

Tuning the morphology of mesoscopic structures of porphyrin macrocycles functionalized by an antimicrobial peptide

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ABSTRACT: The aggregation properties of two peptide-porphyrin conjugates were investigated by optical spectroscopy and microscopy imaging with nanometer resolution. Specifically, a tetraphenylporphyrin platform was functionalized by (L)-magainin, a 23-residue long antimicrobial peptide, and a (L)-magainin analogue differing from the parent peptide by a single residue substitution, i.e. an Ala vs Phe replacement in the position 5 of the peptide chain. Spectroscopic and microscopy results show that this single-site substitution has a small effect on the secondary structure attained by the two peptide analogues, but deeply affects the morphology of the mesoscopic structures deposited on hydrophilic mica from methanol/water solutions. In particular, only the Ala-substituted peptide-porphyrin conjugate was shown to be able to form micrometric fibrils, coating homogeneously a hydrophilic mica surface. These results pave the way for potential applications of porphyrin-peptide compounds in localized photodynamic therapy and for designing solid-state stereoselective sensors.

KEYWORDS: chiral nanostructures, hierarchical self-assembly, hybrid materials, organic coating, porphyrin-peptide conjugates

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INTRODUCTION

Porphyrin-based materials have been deeply investigated as photosensitizing agents in photodynamic therapy (PDT) of tumors for their unique cytotoxic properties [1]. Recently, it has been proposed to use the same approach as an alternative strategy for antimicrobial therapy, due to the increasing resistance of bacterial infection to the available antibiotics [2]. PDT may secure a broad-band antimicrobial activity, exerting cytotoxic effect through non specific oxidative stress on multiple targets.

The charge of the photosensitizer (PS) is an important factor, that determines the selective interaction of positively charged PS's against GRAM-negative bacteria. One strategy to enhance the activity of neutral PS's against GRAM-negative bacteria is to functionalize the PS agent with antimicrobial peptides (CAMPs). It has been shown that the cationic nature of CAMPs strongly promotes the interaction of hydrophobic PS's with procariotic membranes [3-5].

Moreover, the affinity of cationic peptides for the membrane can be modulated by including in the peptide sequence hydrophobic residues, conferring amphiphilic character to the peptide. This property enhances the membrane permeabilization capacity of CAMPs and, therefore, their cytotoxic activity.

Recently, some of us studied several covalently-linked peptide-porphyrin compounds for PDT applications [6,7]. Several CAMPs, i.e. apidaecin Ib, buforin II and magainin 2, were used to enhance the internalization of porphyrin photosensitizer against target cells and to improve the solubility of hydrophobic porphyrins in a biological milieu.

In particular, it was found that aggregation of TPP-magainin as large chiral supramolecular structures was promoted when the peptide attained a stable α -helical conformation, suggesting a templating effect of the peptide secondary structure [8].

Aggregation of the peptide-porphyrin compounds was easily monitored by the marked bathochromic and hypsochromic shift of the porphyrin absorption features and the sensible quenching of its fluorescence emission. A marked reduction of singlet oxygen production was also observed [6,9].

Circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopic studies carried out in both the peptide and porphyrin absorption regions demonstrated that the configuration of the amino acid covalently bound to the macrocycle determined the chiral arrangement of the obtained supramolecular mesoscopic structure [8,9]. Interestingly, the CD spectrum of TPP-(L)-magainin was characterized by an intense exciton splitting of the Soret transition band. The positive/negative signature of the bisignate CD band suggested the anticlockwise winding of the excitonically coupled porphyrin units, organized in helical aggregates of mesoscopic size [10]. This finding emphasizes the role of the intrinsically chiral peptide chains to orient the winding of the helically arranged porphyrin macrocycles.

We have recently shown that the morphology of peptide aggregates in aqueous solutions are determined by the subtle balance of structural features, determining the conformational and dynamical properties of the peptide chain, and environmental (hydrophobic) effects [11].

In particular, we have observed that the formation of peptide fibrils is promoted by the population of helical conformation, and that this structural feature determines by hierarchical self-assembly the morphology of mesoscopic supramolecular architectures. A single amino acid substitution is sufficient to destroy the anisotropic 3D arrangement of the peptide aggregate, giving rise to the formation of globular structures, as a result of predominant hydrophobic effects [12].

Recent studies carried out by our group have been focused on the effect of the presence of an amino acid residue and other chiral substituents on the periphery of related macrocycles. We have shown that such functionalization gave rise to the formation by hierarchical self-assembly of mesoscopic structures featuring supramolecular chirality [13, 14].

In this contribution, we report on the aggregation properties of two peptide-porphyrin compounds comprising a tetraphenylporphyrin unit suitably derivatized at the meso position with a carboxylic group for linking (L)-magainin, a 23-residue antimicrobial peptide, or a magainin analogue, characterized by a single Ala vs Phe modification in the position 5 of the peptide chain. The two compounds, the molecular structures of which are reported in Chart 1, will be denoted in the following as **TPPMag** (MW= 3470 g/mol) and **TPPMagA5** (MW=3547 g/mol), respectively.

The presence of charged and polar amino acids alternated to non polar residues, together with the electron-rich, aromatic porphyrin platform conferred to the two compounds investigated a strong amphiphilic character, that can be usefully exploited to study their aggregation properties in methanol/water solutions. It will be shown that a single-site substitution of an aromatic residue (Phe) with an apolar amino acid (Ala) deeply affects the 3D morphology of porphyrin-peptide aggregates of mesoscopic size.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis

The synthesis of the peptide-porphyrin compounds here investigated was already reported elsewhere [8]. Briefly, peptides were prepared on an automated Advanced Chemtech 348 Ω peptide synthesizer, on a 0.05 mmol scale, starting from preloaded Wang resins (resin substitution 0.51–0.72 mmol g⁻¹). Fmoc deprotection was achieved with 20% piperidine in DMF. Couplings were performed in the presence of O-(benzotriazol-1-yl)N,N,N',N'-tetramethyluronium hexafluorophosphate/N-hydroxybenzotriazole/N,N-diisopropylethylamine or O-(7-azabenzotriazol-1-yl)N,N,N',N'-tetramethyluronium hexafluoro-phosphate/N-hydroxy-7-azabenzotriazole/N,N-diisopropylethylamine (reaction time 45–60 min), using an excess of 4 equivalents of the carboxyl component. For the conjugation to the porphyrin, the H-peptide-resin (0.025 mmol) was swelled in DMF, the solvent was drained off and 600 μ L of a DMF–CH₂Cl₂ solution (1 : 1 v/v) containing 0.05 mmol of TPP-OH, 0.05 mmol diisopropylcarbodiimide and 0.05 mmol 1-hydroxybenzotriazole was added.

Spectroscopy and microscopy techniques

Spectroscopic grade solvents (MeOH, DMSO, CHCl₃) were provided by Carlo Erba reagents (Milan, Italy), and used without further purification. Concentrations were determined by UV-Vis absorption measurements at $\lambda=414$ nm (Soret band), assuming a molar extinction coefficient $\epsilon(414)=400000$ M⁻¹·cm⁻¹ in methanol [14]. UV-Vis absorption measurements were carried out on a CaryWin 100 spectrophotometer (Cary, USA), using quartz cells of appropriate path length (Hellma). Fluorescence measurements have been carried out with a Fluoromax-4 (Horiba), with single photon counting detection, using quartz cells (Hellma). Circular Dichroism spectra were obtained by a JASCO J600 spectropolarimeter (JASCO, Japan). The reported spectra have been obtained by the average of 8 repeated spectra.

Atomic Force Microscopy experiments were carried out in air at room temperature on a Veeco Multiprobe IIIa instrument (Santa Barbara, CA). The AFM measurements were carried out in tapping mode on films obtained by drop casting micromolar methanol and methanol/water 30/70 (v/v) solutions of **TPPMag** and **TPPMagA5** on mica, and

incubating for 18 h in a dryer. For the AFM measurements, a Si super sharp tip, functionalized by Carbon flake was used (curvature 1 nm, elastic constant 5 N/m, resonance frequency 150 kHz).

< Chart 1 >

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Spectroscopic characterization of peptide-porphyrin compounds in solution

The spectroscopic properties of **TPPMag** and **TPPMagA5** in methanol and methanol/water (m/w) mixtures were characterized by UV-Vis absorption, steady-state fluorescence and circular dichroism (CD) experiments. In the former solvent the absorption spectra of the two compounds in the visible region are dominated by the porphyrin absorption bands, i.e. the intense Soret band at $\lambda_{\max}=414$ nm [$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$, $\epsilon(414)=4.0 \cdot 10^5$ mol⁻¹cm⁻¹], and the fourfold Q bands [$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$, $\epsilon(515)=1.0 \cdot 10^4$ mol⁻¹cm⁻¹] at $\lambda_{\max}=515, 550, 590$ and 645 nm, typical of free-base porphyrins. In the case of **TPPMag** the Q-band absorptions appear to be slightly shifted to longer wavelengths, i.e. $\lambda_{\max}=513, 549, 588$ and 644 nm. For both compounds the fluorescence emission spectra showed a single emission band peaked at $\lambda_{\max}=646$ nm.

The aggregation of **TPPMag** and **TPPMagA5** at micromolar concentration was promoted by exploiting the hydrophobic effect exerted by increasing the fraction of water in m/w solutions. Figure 1A showed the UV-Vis absorption spectra of **TPPMagA5** (6.6 μ M) in methanol and in 70/30, 50/50 and 30/70 (v/v) m/w solutions. Upon increasing the content of water in the m/w solutions, a significant decrease of the intensity and a remarkable broadening of the Soret absorption band were observed. The red shift of the absorption band at high water content strongly suggests the formation of J-type aggregates, i.e. ground-state complexes characterized by a head-to-tail stacking of the interacting porphyrin macrocycles [15].

The absorption spectrum of **TPPMag** in 30/70 (v/v) m/w solution also revealed a similar intensity decrease, red shift ($\lambda_{\max}=422$ nm) and broadening of the Soret transition (Figure 1B).

<Fig. 1>

The fluorescence emission spectra of **TPPMagA5** and **TPPMag**, carried out under the same experimental conditions of UV-Vis absorption measurements, strengthen the idea of J-type aggregation, showing decreasing fluorescence emissions and slightly red-shifted maximum emission wavelengths ($\lambda_{\max}=648$ nm) with increasing the water content of m/w solutions (Figure 2). It should be noted that for both compounds the fluorescence excitation spectra overlap the visible absorption spectra, ruling out the formation of fluorescent excited-state species.

<Fig. 2>

The CD spectra of **TPPMagA5** and **TPPMag** in both the amide (200-250 nm) and Soret porphyrin (350-500 nm) transition regions were reported in Figure 3. Analyzing the amide region of the spectra, it can be observed that for both the compounds the peptide chain attains a α -helical conformation under all experimental conditions, i.e. in methanol and in the m/w solutions investigated.

Interestingly, under aggregating conditions, i.e. at the higher water fractions of the m/w solutions, a bisignate curve, typical of electronic transitions excitonically-coupled over extended mesoscopic lengths, can be observed in the porphyrin Soret transition region. The positive/negative profile of these bands is characteristic of a helical anti-clockwise arrangement of the peptide-porphyrin chiral supramolecular structure. It should be noted that these chiroptical bands showed only negligible intensities in methanol and methanol/water 70/30 solutions.

Detailed CD studies on peptide analogs demonstrated that a direct correlation between the helix screw sense of peptide aggregates and the sign of the induced CD bands cannot be found, pointing altogether toward a specific role played by the configuration of the first few residues connecting the porphyrin ring to the peptide chain [8].

<Fig. 3>

Intense bisignate CD bands in the Soret region have often been observed for porphyrin aggregates, and are considered to be diagnostic of the formation of mesoscopic structures [16, 17]. Interestingly, Castriciano et al. established that bisignate CD signals originated from porphyrin aggregates formed at least by 200 regularly arranged porphyrin macrocycles [18]. It has also been shown that the clockwise/anticlockwise winding of helical coiled/coil porphyrin rods can be controlled by a proper selection of chiral groups functionalizing the porphyrin macrocycle [19].

Atomic Force Microscopy experiments

The morphology of **TPPMagA5** and **TPPMag** aggregates deposited on mica by drop casting from micromolar methanol and 30/70 (v/v) m/w solutions has been characterized by AFM measurements.

In the case of deposition from methanol solutions, AFM imaging of both the porphyrin-peptide compounds investigated showed micrometric globular structures of different size distribution. From the data reported in Figure 4A, for **TPPMagA5** an average volume of $4.1(\pm 0.8) \cdot 10^{-3} \mu\text{m}^3$ and area of $1.3(\pm 0.2) \cdot 10^{-1} \mu\text{m}^2$ can be estimated. Interestingly, **TPPMag** showed definitely smaller globular structures, the average volume and area being $8.3(\pm 1.2) \cdot 10^{-5} \mu\text{m}^3$ and $9.4(\pm 1.1) \cdot 10^{-3} \mu\text{m}^2$, respectively (Figure 4B). In Supporting Information the histograms of volumes and areas of the mesoscopic structures formed by the two covalently-linked peptide-porphyrin compounds have been reported (Figures SI1, SI2). It should be noted that a globular morphology allows to obtain the maximum inner density with the minimum outer surface.

<Fig. 4>

Interestingly, in a restricted area of **TPPMagA5** on mica, but not for **TPPMag**, rods of micrometric length and nanometric width (70-85 nm) and height (1.5-1.7 nm) could be observed. At higher resolution these rods appear to be formed by intertwined nanometric filaments (Figure 5).

<Fig. 5>

Upon drop casting deposition on a mica surface of a methanol/water 30/70 micromolar **TPPMagA5** solution, AFM imaging showed the formation of a dense network of fibril structures coating almost homogeneously the solid substrate (Figure 6).

From Figure 6B, it can be seen how the observed fibril structures, having a characteristic length of 217 (± 14) nm, are formed by intertwined thin filaments, showing 43.7 (± 0.7) nm width and 2.3 (± 0.2) nm height.

<Fig. 6>

In the case of deposition on mica of a micromolar TPPMag solution carried out under aggregating conditions, i.e. in methanol/water 30/70, AFM imaging experiments only revealed the presence of large agglomerates of globular shape (Figure 7). In Figure 7B, a thin filament connecting two globular structures can be observed. Analyzing the AFM profiles of the three sections depicted in the figure, the filament was found to have a length of 474 nm, an average width of 29 (± 2) nm, and height of 3.7 (± 0.1) nm.

It should be noted that the generation of fibrils from clusters of aligned globular structures has also been observed in the case of amyloid fibrillization, a process responsible for the onset of degenerative neurological diseases [19]. Interestingly, a similar behavior was observed by us in the case of aggregates of steroid porphyrin derivatives in analogous media [20].

<Fig. 7>

Figure 8 shows a gross TPPMag fibril decorated with globular aggregates and a thin filament connecting two of such globules.

<Fig. 8>

CONCLUSION

The mesoscopic structures imaged by AFM experiments are the result of the combined effect of two topological motifs: (i) the stacking interaction between the electron-rich porphyrin moieties able to propagate the geometric properties of porphyrin dimers (J- or H-aggregates) over micrometric lengths, and (ii) the helical structure of the peptide chains, functionalizing the porphyrin macrocycle. By hierarchical self-assembly, these structural motifs determine the morphology of the globular or rod-like aggregates propagating the conformational properties of the peptide-porphyrin building blocks to the mesoscopic scale.

It should be noted that the chiral arrangement of the porphyrin supramolecular architectures does not depend on the screw-sense of the peptide helix, but on the conformational properties and hydrophobic nature of the very few residues connecting the porphyrin macrocycle to the peptide chain.

As a consequence, the Ala vs Phe single-site substitution that distinguishes TPPMagA5 from TPPMag has a deep effect on the morphology of the mesoscopic structures imaged by AFM experiments, although the secondary structure of the two peptide analogues, monitored by CD measurements, appear definitely similar. The Phe residue has been deeply investigated,

due to its capacity to give rise to a rich morphology of peptide nano- and mesostructures, strictly depending on the specific experimental conditions under which the self-assembly process was conducted [21].

The mechanism of fibril formation has been thoroughly investigated for its importance in the early steps of neurodegenerative diseases [22] and in controlled self-assembly of nano- and mesostructures for nanotechnology applications [23, 24].

In this regard, the imaging of globular structures connected by filament-like segments gives some insight on the potential intermediate structures bridging the globule-to-fibril transition.

These results would be of great importance, among others, for the development of solid-state sensors featuring stereoselective properties, presently pursued in our group [25-28].

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Chart 1. Molecular structures and acronyms of the investigated peptide-porphyrin conjugates.

Fig. 1 Visible absorption spectra. (A) **TPPMagA5**: a) MeOH, b) MeOH/H₂O 70:30, c) MeOH/H₂O 50:50, d) MeOH/H₂O 30:70; (B) **TPPMag**: a) MeOH, b) MeOH/H₂O 30:70.

Fig. 2 Fluorescence emission spectra of (A) **TPPMagA5**: MeOH (a), MeOH/H₂O 70:30 (b), MeOH/H₂O 50:50 (c), MeOH/H₂O 30:70 (d); (B) **TPPMag**: MeOH (a), MeOH/H₂O 30:70 (b).

Fig. 3 CD spectra of **TPPMagA5** (A,C) and **TPPMag** (B,D) in the peptide UV (A,B) and porphyrin Soret transition (C,D) regions. Black: MeOH; green: MeOH/H₂O 70/30; red: MeOH/H₂O 50/50; blue: MeOH/H₂O 20/80 (v/v).

Fig. 4 AFM images obtained from drop casting deposition on mica of micromolar methanol solution of **TPPMagA5** (A) and **TPPMag** (B).

Fig. 5 A) AFM images obtained from drop casting deposition on mica of micromolar methanol solution of **TPPMagA5**. B) Nanometric magnification of the rod structures observed in A). Thinner filaments could be observed along the 1-4 numbered sections.

<i>Fibrils</i>	<i>Length(nm)</i>
<i>1</i>	192
<i>2</i>	238
<i>3</i>	230
<i>4</i>	262
<i>5</i>	276
<i>6</i>	238
<i>7</i>	330
<i>8</i>	172
<i>9</i>	144
<i>10</i>	188
<i>11</i>	108
<i>12</i>	210
<i>13</i>	261
<i>14</i>	197
<i>15</i>	213
<i>Average</i>	217 ± 14

	<i>Width (nm)</i>	<i>Height (nm)</i>
<i>1</i>	44.6	2.2
<i>2</i>	43.0	2.1
<i>3</i>	43.4	2.6
<i>Average</i>	43.7 ± 0.7	2.3 ± 0.2

Fig. 6 A): AFM image of TPPMagA5 nanofibers obtained after deposition of TPPMagA5 0.4 μ M in methanol/water 30/70 (v/v). B): Imaging of a TPPMagA5 fiber, showing the intimate structure of intertwined filaments. On the right the morphological features of the nanofibrils imaged in A) and B) are reported.

<i>Section</i>	<i>Width (nm)</i>	<i>Height (nm)</i>
1	26.6	3.7
2	26.5	3.8
3	33.1	3.6
<i>Average</i>	28.7 ± 2.2	3.7 ± 0.1

Fig. 7 A): AFM image of TPPMag agglomerates obtained after deposition on mica of TPPMag in methanol/water 30/70 (v/v). B): Magnification of the boxed area in Figure 6A, showing small clusters of globular structures. A single filament connecting two globular structures can also be observed in the Figure 7B.

Fig. 8. AFM image obtained after deposition on mica of **TPPMag** in methanol/water 30/70 (v/v). A gross fiber structures decorated with bright globules can be clearly envisaged, as well as the thin filament connecting two globule structures. Widths and heights of the latter filament along the numbered sections depicted in the AFM image are also reported.

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